

University Librarians' Perception and Attitude towards Adoption of Makerspace as Supportive Tools for "Steam" Education and Learning in Kano State Universities

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Abstract

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Introduction: This study investigated university librarians' perceptions and attitudes towards the adoption of makerspaces within their libraries as supportive tools for STEAM education in Kano State, Nigeria. The research was guided by five key objectives.

Method: The study employed a qualitative approach using judgmental sampling techniques to select university libraries across six universities in Kano State. Participants comprised university librarians from these six universities. An interview protocol was developed and sent to participants, seeking their consent and assuring confidentiality and anonymity. Asynchronous email interviews were conducted with each participant from July 16, 2020, to August 11, 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Results/Findings: Thematic analysis revealed that university librarians have a growing awareness of the potential of makerspaces, recognize their role in STEAM education, and have overwhelmingly positive perceptions and attitudes towards adopting makerspaces. While some universities possess plans and necessary infrastructure for makerspaces, challenges such as funding, space, and skilled staff shortages exist.

Conclusion: The study concludes that while university librarians in Kano State are generally positive about adopting makerspaces and recognize their importance in STEAM education, several challenges must be addressed to facilitate successful implementation.

Recommendations: The study recommends addressing challenges related to funding, space, and skilled staff shortages to ensure the successful implementation of makerspaces. These steps will enhance learning, creativity, and innovation in universities within Kano State.

Introduction:

Sciences, Technology, Engineering, Arts & Maths (STEAM) Education has become an integral element of tertiary education and now acts as a catalyst of transformation aimed at employing strategies that equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge requirements of the 21st century workforce. This educational approach involves creative processes with multiple methods for inquiry and investigation. Thus, teaching relevant, in-demand skills that will prepare students to become innovators in an ever-evolving world is paramount for the future of the students and the country (Lathan, 2020) at large.

In today's world, preparing students for future success means exposing them to these disciplines holistically to develop their critical thinking skills. Beyond the classroom, students use different models such as sketches, diagrams, mathematical relationships, simulations and physical models to predict the likely behaviour of a system. To achieve this, they need a space, the technology, equipment, facilities to collect and gather relevant data that will help them in evaluating their predictions. The low-tech and high-tech avails the students' tools and methods to explore new and creative ways of problem-solving, displaying data, innovating, and linking multiple fields.

The cultural evolution from more traditional approaches toward technological changes forces, libraries now to position themselves as community centers, offering an array of educational programs and services. Recent trends in Librarianship point to themes of crafting, artisans, creators, and makers in library spaces. One of these trends is the Maker Movement, which calls for the return of the artisans, creators and makers and how libraries can support these movements and entrepreneurs (Filar Williams & Folkman, 2017). Academic libraries are on a never-ending continuum to get their users to the library and makerspace initiative creates that

impulse by bringing together innovators, thinkers, creators, technology, physical space, integrated platforms, human and finances resources to make their idea a realistic one.

A makerspace is a collaborative work space inside a school, library or separated public/private facility for making, learning, exploring and sharing, that uses "high tech. to no tech. tools". These spaces are open to kids, adults, and entrepreneurs and have a variety of maker equipment including 3D printers, laser cutters, CNC machines, soldering irons and even sewing machines. A makerspace however doesn't need to include all of these machines or even any of them to be considered a makerspace (Makerspaces, 2020). These spaces help in preparing those who need the critical 21st century skills in the fields of science, technology, engineering, arts, & the maths. They provide hands on learning, help with critical thinking skills and even boost self-confidence.

With the influence of technology, the academic libraries assumed different attributes and devised new approaches to library operations to cope with the present global audience. The justification for having makerspaces in academic libraries is because they provide access to a wide variety of tools and technology; facilitate group interaction, knowledge, and resource sharing; supply access to physical space for individual project development; provide an open environment for expression of creativity and innovation; access to equipment for prototyping project ideas for companies; community empowerment; foster community collaboration and co-creation; inter-generational learning and social connectedness, developing a culture of lifelong learning and adding socio-economic advantage to communities and provide an opportunity for libraries to future-proof themselves and adapt to meet the changing nature of society.

As makerspaces develop from a trend to a core service in academic libraries, its actualization depends more on the university librarian's ability to prepare a good proposal that will convince the university management to accept and implement it in their university libraries.

Research Problem:

There is a growing need to equip students with the skills and knowledge necessary to succeed in the 21st-century economy, which is increasingly driven by science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics (STEAM). Makerspaces, which are physical spaces equipped with tools and technologies that encourage creativity, innovation, and hands-on learning, are emerging as valuable resources for STEAM education. However, the potential of makerspaces in Kano State university libraries remains largely untapped due to a lack of understanding and support from university librarians who play a crucial role in shaping the learning environment.

This is evidently seen in a study conducted by Ladan and Adamu (2023), and Osawaru, Dime, & Okonjo, (2020) which highlighted a number of problems hindering the adoption of makerspaces in Kano State universities. These problems include librarians' lack of sufficient understanding about makerspaces, potential benefits for STEAM education, and how they can be implemented effectively within libraries. Lack of dedicated funding and resources, erratic power supply, resistance to change, traditional library practices, and limited collaboration between librarians and other stakeholders. These problems may have a significant impact in establishing makerspace in academic libraries in Nigeria.

Research Objectives:

The specific research objectives are: -

1. To examine the university librarians' knowledge and understanding of makerspaces.
2. To investigate the perceived role of university librarians in supporting and facilitating STEAM Education and learning through makerspace.
3. To examine the university librarians' attitudes towards the adoption of makerspaces within their university libraries.
4. To ascertain the level of planning/implementation of makerspaces in their university libraries.
5. To identify challenges to having makerspaces in university libraries in Kano State.

Makerspaces and STEAM Education:

Makerspaces, also commonly known as hackerpaces, makerlabs, or fablabs trace their origins to the 1990s when educators began outreach to community members interested in creating or tinkering with materials; the concept took popular hold beginning in the mid to late 2000s (EDUCAUSE, 2013). The force behind the initial "maker movement" is believed to be the creation of Make: magazine in 2005, which published information about maker-related projects. The momentum grew when the magazine devised a series of venues for makers to express themselves and share their creations deemed "maker faires". Libraries took notice and began offering programs and redesigning spaces to address related interests within their communities (Wikipedia, 2020).

Makerspaces, are spaces where individuals or groups converge to get innovative with Do-it-yourself (DIY) projects, share ideas and invent new ones (Okuonghae, 2019). Makerspace is an area in a library where users can use tools and equipment to design, build, and create all sorts of different things. It may be a dedicated room or a multipurpose space in which a collection of raw materials and

resources can be utilized as desired. Waters (2020), offers a very viable discussion of the importance of the makerspace on campus. She stated that makerspaces work, and their values should be encouraged because they include: Small group discussions; Collaboration; Participatory and peer to peer project-based learning; Participation; Inquiry; Curiosity, and Fun.

On the other hand, STEAM stands for Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Math-a powerful combination of topics and techniques for educating our society (STEAMResources, 2020). STEAM represents a paradigm shift from traditional education philosophy, based on standardized test scores, to a modern ideal which focuses on valuing the learning process as much as the results. In essence, the students are dared to be wrong, to try multiple ideas, listen to alternate opinions and create a knowledge base that is applicable to real life as opposed to simply an exam (Cameron, 2020). STEAMResources (2020) emphasised that, the STEAM movement originated at the Rhode Island School of Design (RISD) and has since been widely adopted among many institutions and organizations. The objectives of the STEAM movement were created to do the following:

- a. Transform research policy to place art and design at the center of STEAM
- b. Encourage integration of art and design in education
- c. Influence employers to hire artists and designers to drive innovation

To this end, Makerspaces and STEAM education is considered as a central place for learning, critical thinking, inquiry, knowledge creation, collaborative learning and discovery take place through hands on creation, via use of any combination of analog art and technology (low-tech) and digital (high tech). Makerspaces and STEAM education are expected to enhance creativity and innovativeness in students, work with their

peers, consider new ideas, explore, tinker, invent and make.

Academic Libraries and Makerspaces

Academic libraries are now changing from repositories of materials to collaborative spaces for learning by positioning themselves as community centers, offering an array of educational programs and services (Hardenbrook, 2017). Okpala, (2019) gave some reasons for establishing makerspaces in academic libraries where it served as a central place for learning; innovation; a place for knowledge creation; marketing of library services and equitable access to new technologies. Hardenbrook, (2017) conducted research on making sense of makerspaces in academic library where it revealed that makerspace houses equipment such as PCs for 3D design, two 3D printers, two 3D scanners, an electronic cutter, a sewing machine, a painting and college station, and a coloring station (e.g., coloring books). Makerspaces and varying new technologies are exciting services now being offered in libraries, particularly academic libraries.

As universities look for ways to encourage innovation and entrepreneurship, many academic libraries have begun providing access to maker resources and services. In 2012, DeLaMare Science & Engineering Library became one of the first academic libraries to provide maker resources and services to anyone, regardless of discipline or even university affiliation (Radniecki and Klenke, 2017). Makerspaces provide an opportunity for academic libraries to build upon services they already offer while reaching students and faculty members who do not frequent the library on a daily basis. Implementing a makerspace in academic libraries will transform it to be more neutral and approachable by students and staff from all academic departments.

Benefits of Library Makerspaces to STEAM Learners

Library users or STEAM Learners benefit from makerspaces in a number of ways as it enables them to learn, create, use and share DIY knowledge. Library makerspaces are cheap, or sometimes free with no admission cost (Okuonghae, 2019). According to Julian and Parrott (2017), academic libraries already nurture critical thinking and learning, they are a perfect environment for makerspaces. They further stressed that, involving the library in promoting STEAM proficiency is an extremely important key to reaching a wide variety of people of all ages and backgrounds. Library programs can benefit STEAM learners by offering everyone learning opportunities that spark curiosity and build interest in STEAM subjects.

Rosheim (2020) identified the benefits of library makerspaces to STEAM learners as: it allow participants to embrace failure as a means for heading toward success; allow participants to collaborate and learn from one another; create experts whom participants will look to for guidance; foster creative thinking; create ways for participants to ask real questions to drive their exploration; encourage participants to pursue existing passions or seek out new passions; ignite excitement and a joy for learning; promote multiple ways to solve problems; allow participants to practice perseverance in day to day learning; expose participants to materials they may have never used before: 3D printers, robotic balls, textile materials, circuits, littleBits, programming, and so much more; encourage participant reflection on the process of making; and create thinkers.

Requirements for Set-up Makerspace in Academic Libraries

According to Crumpton (2015), there are certain criteria for setting up academic library maker-space, these include guidelines, and policies that protect maker-space users such as intellectual freedom, and privacy in order

to protect whatever is being produced, or innovated within the area. Okuonghae, (2019) pointed out that, setting up a makerspace in libraries goes beyond finding the right space. It also entails getting the library users active and identifying leaders and mentors to take charge. Further outlines the following requirements for setting up a makerspace in academic libraries.

1. Makerspace policy and goals;
2. The right space;
3. Makerspace theme or program for the target audience;
4. Funding for getting the right tools and materials;
5. Identify training and support expert/mentors for the program.

Challenges of Implementing Makerspaces in Academic Libraries

According to Okuonghae (2019), the adoption of a new innovation is always welcome with numerous challenges. In Nigeria, the challenge of implementing a new idea is even greater when such idea involves the use of technological gadget. Stressing that, the introduction of makerspaces in Nigerian libraries has been faced with different challenges despite the numerous benefits derived from makerspaces in libraries. Okpala (2016) identified some of the challenges of implementing a makerspace project in academic libraries as: challenge of training the users; security challenges; funding issues; lack of sufficient space in the library building; erratic power supply; technophobia; and high cost and maintenance of equipment, Internet bandwidth, hardware and software.

Aiyebilehin, Onyam and Akpom (2018) explained that, some of the challenges facing makerspaces in Nigerian libraries are perennial problems affecting all ICT related projects in Nigerian libraries. These challenges ranges from negative perception of traditional librarians, poor funding of libraries, lack of librarians' willingness to adopt innovative strategies in library, to lack

of trained personnel to handle the maker Spaces. In addition to poor level of awareness of the concept of maker Spaces among librarians, there is the issue of poor storage facilities and poor maintenance culture of library infrastructures.

Methodology

Qualitative research methodology was employed using case study design that allows the researcher to explore the experiences and perspectives of each respondent in detail, gathering rich qualitative data. Non-probability sampling was applied using the judgemental sampling techniques in selecting the participants and sites in order to understand the central phenomenon through the use of asynchronous email interview. This method allows exchange of information repeatedly online between researcher and participant within a particular time-frame (Ratislavová & Ratislav, 2014). The justification of using this method was due to Covid-19 pandemic as movement and gathering were restricted in order to maintained social distance. Thus, the participants comprised of university librarians drawn from the six (6) universities within Kano State in-respective of their status (Skyline University Nigeria; Bayero University, Kano; Yusuf Maitama Sule University, Kano; Kano University of Science & Technology, Wudil; Nigerian Police Academy, Wudil; & Al-istiqama University Sumaila.). Interview protocol was developed

and sent to the targeted participants seeking their consent for participation as well as assuring the participants confidentiality and anonymity. The email interview was scheduled and held with each participant on different occasions specifically from 16th July, 2020 to 11th August, 2020. Content analysis was adopted using thematic analysis technique that identify recurring themes and patterns across the emails by coding different parts of the text for meaning and grouping them into relevant categories. This helps understand the overall attitudes, experiences, and opinions expressed by the participants.

Presentation and Analysis of Data:

This section deals with presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected from the participants. Thematic analysis technique was used to analyze the interview text of the participants. Themes that emerged from the data were used to report the findings of the study. The themes that emerged were: -

Theme 1: Knowledge and Understanding on Makerspace.

Theme 2: University Librarians Support for STEAM Education.

Theme 3: Opinion on Having a Makerspace in Academic Libraries.

Theme 4: Efforts / Plans for Having Makerspace.

Theme 5: Challenges.

Table 1.0: Codes Ascribed to the Participants of Each Institution

S/N	Institutions	Code	University Librarian
1	SUN	C1	1
2	BUK	C2	1
3	YUMSUK	C3	1
4	KUST	C4	1
5	NPA	C5	1
6	AL-ISTIQAMA	C6	1

Table 1.0 shows the codes assigned to the participants of each institution. The codes conformed to the use of thematic method of

analysis when qualitative method is adopted in research. Code C1 was assigned to Skyline University Nigeria, Code C2 to Bayero

University Kano, Code C3 to Yusuf Maitama Sule University Kano, C4 to Kano State University of Science and Technology Wudil, C5 to Nigerian Police Academy, Wudil, and finally C6 was assigned to Al-istiqlama University Sumaila. A total number of six (6) participants participated in this research, one from each institution.

University Librarians' Knowledge and Understanding on Makerspace

Research Objective 1. Participants were asked to describe and give their knowledge and understanding on makerspace. The response were as follows: -

C1:- *“The interviewee highlights the emerging concept of makerspaces, where individuals can gather and acquire creative skills through active participation. They emphasize the importance of physical engagement and interaction in the learning process, while acknowledging the optional use of technology. Furthermore, they propose that libraries should embrace their potential as practical training centers for their user communities”.*

C2:- *“This interviewee views makerspaces as empowering environments for young people. They perceive them as offering two key opportunities: Exploration and self-discovery: Young people can explore their own interests and passions in a supportive and encouraging setting. Creative project development: They can learn to use various tools and materials, both physical and digital, to bring their creative ideas to life through tangible projects”.*

C3:- *“This interviewee envisions makerspaces as dynamic areas within libraries, overflowing with possibilities for users to create, experiment, and learn. They see them*

as a break from traditional, book-centric libraries, offering: A hands-on playground: Users can design, build, and create diverse projects, venturing beyond the confines of reading rooms. Unleashing creative potential: The space encourages thinking outside the box, fostering collaboration, learning new skills, and exploring innovative ideas. Technology as a catalyst: Tools like computers and 3D printers become facilitators for creative expression, not just passive information sources. A learning ecosystem: The interviewee emphasizes the educational and learning aspects of makerspaces, aiming to provide environments that nurture individual and collective growth”.

C4:- *“The interviewee sees makerspaces as creative havens within libraries, equipped with tools that empower users to unleash their potential in their chosen fields. These spaces provide fertile ground for individuals to: Tap into their creativity: Users can delve into their unique areas of interest, experimenting and expressing themselves freely. Fuel innovation: The environment encourages users to push boundaries, think outside the box, and generate fresh ideas. Unlock potential: Equipped with the necessary tools, individuals can discover and nurture their hidden talents and abilities”.*

C5:- *“The interviewee defines a makerspace as a versatile “making” hub, located within schools, libraries, or even dedicated facilities. It fosters collaboration, learning, exploration, and open sharing, embracing a spectrum of tools from high-tech gadgets to everyday materials”.*

C6:- “The interviewee paints a vibrant picture of makerspaces as collaborative hubs buzzing with creation, learning, and connection. These spaces, found in schools, libraries, or dedicated facilities, welcome everyone - kids, adults, and even entrepreneurs - to explore their maker spirit. From high-tech tools like 3D printers and laser cutters to down-to-earth sewing machines and soldering irons, these spaces provide a diverse playground for building, tinkering, and bringing ideas to life. Collaboration, learning, and open sharing are the cornerstones of this creative ecosystem, encouraging individuals to grow alongside each other”.

Based on the interview excerpts from C1-C6 indicated that university librarians are increasingly aware of the potential of makerspaces for enhancing learning, creativity, and innovation within their institutions. This means that, the participants are familiar with the concept of makerspace as their perceptions is in line with the definitions of scholars such as Burke (2014); Pisarski (2014) and Okuonghae, (2019). Thus, based on the participants’ description and understanding of makerspace, one could say that, they are aware with the concept of makerspace in academic libraries.

University Librarians Support for STEAM Education

Research Objective 2. Participants were asked on the ways they think university librarians can support Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts & the Maths (STEAM) education. The response were as follows: -

C1:- “The interviewee, expresses a strong commitment to supporting STEAM education by ensuring the establishment makerspace within the library as a key strategic move towards achieving this goal”.

C2:- “This passionate interviewee sees librarians as pioneers, transforming libraries into vibrant STEAM playgrounds with makerspaces that allow students explore and master STEAM disciplines through hands-on experiences as learning goes beyond textbooks”.

C3:- “The interviewee sees establishing makerspaces as a game-changer for university libraries, offering multifaceted support for enhanced learning, fosters various learning styles, embracing different literacy practices and encouraging exploration beyond typical classroom settings”.

C4:- “The interviewee expresses eagerness to partner with university management in establishing a makerspace. They envision this space as a **support hub** empowering users”.

C5:- “The interviewee advocates for dedicated resources and space within the university library to support STEAM education. Believes that this will foster hands-on learning, critical thinking skills, and enhanced self-confidence”.

C6:- “This interviewee sees the makerspace as a fertile ground for nurturing tomorrow's architects, innovators, and artists, providing them with the space, resources, and encouragement to blossom into their full potential”.

Based on these submissions, interview excerpts revealed university librarians could serve as crucial actors in supporting and facilitating STEAM education through makerspaces. They envision themselves as proactive instigators, active facilitators, and empowering mentors, playing a vital role in shaping the future of STEAM learning within universities. This is in line with Baek, (2013) and Abram (2013) where they stated that, librarians and libraries (with makerspaces)

are able to support STEAM learning activities by provide access to a wide variety of tools and technology. This implies that, academic libraries can support the STEAM education through the provision of space, equipment, facilities, policies, and necessary technologies required for learning opportunities.

Attitude of University Librarians on Having Makerspace in Academic Libraries

Research Objective 3. Participants were asked on their opinion of having a makerspace in their academic libraries. The response were as follows: -

C1:- “Yes, I will support this innovation 100% (hundred percent)”.

C2:- “Yes, I will support this innovation”.

C3:- “Yes, I will support this idea”.

C4:- “Yes, I will support it, it is very essential in libraries”.

C5:- “Yes, I will support it because of its great advantage in libraries”.

C2:- “Yes, I will support this development”.

Overall, the excerpts strongly imply that university librarians hold overwhelmingly positive attitudes towards adopting makerspaces within their libraries. They see it as valuable innovations with significant potential to benefit the institution and its users. This is not surprising as rightly observed by Brundy (2015), and German & Namachchivaya, (2013) where they said that, innovation “has moved from a consideration to a necessity” and looking at the reality under which the academic libraries are operating coupled with technological advancement, as well as many research libraries confirming the innovation imperative in their planning documents. Academic libraries must therefore embrace this innovation to remain relevant in the knowledge enterprise space.

4.4 Efforts / Plans for Having Makerspace in Academic Libraries

Research Objective 4. Participants were asked (i) whether they have any plan in future of establishing makerspace in their academic libraries. (ii) If *yes*, what are their plans and If *No*, what would they suggest? (iii) The researchers also went further to asked whether the participants think they have the necessary infrastructure/facilities to start a makerspace in their libraries? The response were as follows: -

(i) *Whether they have any plan in future of establishing makerspace in their libraries;*

C1:- “Yes, we have a plan”.

C2:- “Yes, we have a plan”.

C3:- “No plan at the moment”.

C4:- “No plan at the moment”.

C5:- “Yes, we have a plan in future”.

C6:- “Yes, we have a plan”.

Some have a plan of establishing a makerspace in their libraries while the others not at the moment.

(ii) *If yes, what are their plans and if no what would they suggest;*

C1:- “The interviewee describes their plans to integrate informal education with library services, highlighting a past makerspace session for female users as a successful example. They already tasted success in 2019, hosting a vibrant cake decorating workshop for female users led by a local baking star. The joy and engagement were infectious, boosting library usage and leaving everyone craving more. That's why they're doubling down on this approach, planning to connect even more entrepreneurs with library users, eager to spark creativity, ignite new skills, and open doors to diverse career paths”.

C2:- *“The interviewee sees libraries transforming into bustling centers of knowledge, where individual sparks of curiosity ignite into shared flames of learning. This is the bold vision championed by an interviewee who envisions libraries as bridges, connecting communities, schools, and individuals. By offering a dynamic and inclusive space, brimming with resources both digital and physical, they aim to weave a tapestry of knowledge accessible to all”.*

C3:- *“The interviewee proposes two steps to gauge interest and feasibility for a library makerspace by gather feedback: Conduct a survey or other method to solicit opinions from both library staff and students about their need for a makerspace. Run a pilot project: Establish a temporary "prototype" makerspace in one of the faculty/branch libraries to test its acceptability and effectiveness with users”.*

C4:- *“I suggested that, enough space should be provided first”.*

C5:- *“To conduct a survey for the need of such innovation”.*

C6:- *“The University is planning to construct a new library and intends to include a dedicated space for a makerspace within it”.*

Those that admitted to have a plan indicated that, they integrate the informal education sector by working with entrepreneurs, bringing individuals, community, and schools to allow people to make use of information resources as well as planning to have space meant for makerspace. While those that do not have a plan suggested that, sampling the opinion of both the staff and the students on their need for having a makerspace in their libraries and/or should start as a prototype, in

one of the faculty/branch libraries to see if it is acceptable to users.

(iii) *Regarding infrastructure/facilities;*

C1:- *“Thinks, they have the basic necessary infrastructure and facilities to start makerspace in their library. They also have a well-ventilated room with chairs, and other items. The makerspace is not necessarily to most have a gigantic infrastructure or technological gadgets. Once there is a space, it can be used for a range of activities”.*

C2:- *“They have the necessary infrastructure and facilities for starting a makerspace in their library”.*

C3:- *“They also have the necessary infrastructure and facilities for starting makerspaces in the library”.*

C4:- *“Thinks, that they don't have the necessary infrastructure and facilities for starting makerspaces in their library”.*

C5:- *“Also, thinks, that they don't have the necessary infrastructure and facilities for starting makerspaces in their library”.*

C6:- *“Thinks, that they don't have the necessary infrastructure and facilities for starting makerspaces in their library for now”.*

Based on these submissions, some participants have a plan of establishing a makerspace in their libraries while others do not have it at the moment. They could not also categorically stated their level of preparedness as one said they are liaising with entrepreneur, the other emphasis on change in peoples reading culture and others advocated for conducting a survey. In terms of infrastructure and facilities, it revealed that some have the necessary infrastructure and facilities for starting makerspace while others

do not. This is not in line with Okpala, (2016) on having a makerspace in Nigeria where she stated that, first there is need to identify the need for makerspace, check for available or unused space, talk with the management, define your audience, justify reasons for your makerspace in the library, cite other library makerspaces, prepared a proposal, organize training, develop policy document, budget planning, floor planning and then market your makerspace. This implies that the participants have passion for having makerspace in their libraries but they are not truly prepared for it because having the necessary space, infrastructure and facilities is not enough, it requires some more efforts.

4.5 Challenges

Research Objective 5. Participants were asked on what they think could be the possible obstacles for setting up makerspace in their academic libraries. The response were as follows:-

C1:- “Staff Resistance to Change, and Mentorship Issues”.

C2:- “Lack of Funds / Shrink Budget, Space Issue, Lack of Adequate Skilled Staff, Lack of Interest by Library Staff / Staff Resistance to Change and Incessant Power Outage”.

C3:- “Lack of Funds / Shrink Budget, Lack of Adequate Skilled Staff, and Lack of Interest by Library Staff / Staff Resistance to Change, Low User Patronage of Library and Technophobia as some of the possible challenges”.

C4:- “Funding and disposition of the Head of the library”.

C5:- “Lack of Political will”.

C6:- “Lack of Political will”.

Based on this submission it revealed that, lack of funds / shrink budget, space issue, lack of adequate skilled staff, lack of interest by library staff / staff resistance to change, incessant power outage, mentorship issues, low user patronage of library and

technophobia are some of the challenges that affect the establishment of makerspaces in academic libraries in Nigeria. This is in collaboration with what Aiyebilehin, Onyam and Akpom (2018). This implies that, there is no existing project without challenges, thus the need to prepare ahead of challenges.

Summary of findings:

The study findings revealed that:

1. The participants generally perceived makerplaces to be a place or space(s) created within the library for creativity, innovation, thinking out of the box, making, collaborating and learning new skills;
2. The participants opined that the role of having makerspaces in academic libraries is to support STEAM Education and learning. They believe that academic libraries can support STEAM learning through provision of space for collaboration and partnership and so on;
3. The participants have positive attitude towards makerspaces as they are all willing to support the establishment or having makerspace in their academic libraries; none of the participants indicated lack of interest in having makerspaces in their libraries.
4. Although, the participants did not have any formal plan or space dedicated for makerspace in their libraries, but they believe they have some infrastructure and equipment necessary for makerspace;
5. Lack of funds, space, lack of adequate skilled librarians and lack of interest by library staff or staff resistance to change, incessant power outage, mentorship issues, and technophobia are some of identified challenges affecting the establishment of makerspaces in their libraries.

Conclusion:

Libraries are transforming as technology races forward, they're becoming hubs for learning and creation, not just places to borrow books. One exciting trend is the rise of makerspaces. These hands-on areas allow people of all backgrounds, from hobbyists to entrepreneurs, to tinker with tools and technology. For universities, makerspaces are more than just a fad, they're a game-changer. To truly thrive, libraries need long-term plans for funding, staffing, and equipment. University librarians as leaders should advocate for the establishment of makerspace in academic libraries by seeking university administrator's support towards achieving this initiative.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Though, the University Librarians understood the concept of makerspace, there is need need for vigorous awareness of and advocacy for makerspace by stakeholders such as professional librarians (like University Librarians), and library associations (NLA, LRCN) towards the establishment of makerspaces in academic libraries within Kano State Universities and Nigeria in general.
2. Given the librarians' passion and potential as proactive facilitators as well as the important role that makerspace play in support of teaching STEAM education, there is the need for all university librarians in the state to make conscious effort in initiating a pilot makerspace project within the university libraries.
3. Despite the fact that university librarians are willing and ready to support the establishment of makerspace, there is need to initiate a planning committee that includes the university librarians as key

stakeholders, tasked with developing a concrete proposal for establishing a makerspace within the university library.

4. There is need for vigorous efforts from the University Librarians to identify the need for makerspace, cheeck for available or unused space, talk with the management, define the target audience, justify reasons for the makersapce in the library, cite other library makerspaces, prepared a proposal, organize training, develop policy document, budget planning, floor planning and then marketing the makerspace.
5. There is need for the university management to support this initiative through the provision of resources such as funding, space, infrastructure and equipment, staffing, and training of both staff and students. As this would assist in overcoming the potential challenges of makerspace.

References

- Abram, S. (2013). Makerspaces in libraries, education, and beyond. *Internet@ schools, 20*(2), 18-20.
- Aiyebilehin, J. A., Onyam, I. D., & Akpom, C. C. (2018). Creating Makerspaces in Nigerian Public Libraries as a Strategy for Attaining National Integration and Development. *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology, 8*(4), 19-31.
- Brundy, C. (2015). Academic libraries and innovation: A literature review. *Journal of Library Innovation, 6*(1), 22–39. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/13614533.2019.1697099>
- Burke, J. (2014). Making sense: Can Makerspaces Work in Academic Libraries? *ACRL, 1*-14.

- Burke, J. J. (2014). *Makerspaces: A Practical Guide for Librarians*. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Colegrove, T. (2013). Libraries as makerspace? *Information Technology & Libraries*, 1-4.
- Crumpton, M. A. (2015). Fines, fees and funding: makerspaces standing apart, The Bottom Line. *Managing library finances*, 28(3), 90 – 94.
- DeLaMare Science & Engineering Library. (2017). "Lending Technology,". Retrieved from <http://guides.library.unr.edu/equipment-checkout/delamare>
- Driller, C. (2020). *Maker Cameron*. Retrieved from <https://blogs.library.unt.edu/factory/2020/04/10/maker-cameron/>
- EDUCAUSE. (2013). *EDUCAUSE LEARN INGINITIVE*. Retrieved from <https://library.educause.edu/~media/files/library/2013/4/eli7095-pdf>
- Eke-Okpala, H. N. (2016). Making a makerspace case for academic libraries in Nigeria. *New Library World*, 117((9/10)), 568-586. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/NLW-05-2016-0038>
- German, L., & Namachchivaya, B. S. (2013). *Innovation and R&D. SPEC Kit 339*. Washington, DC: Association of Research Libraries.
- Hardenbrook, J. (2017). Making Sense of Makerspaces: Academic Library Staff Responses to a Makerspace. *Library Dude*, 1-14.
- Julian, K., & Parrott, D. (2017). Makerspaces in the Library: Science in a Student's Hands. *Semantic Scholar*, 1-12.
- Kemrajh, C. K. (2019, June 25). *Makerspaces" in academic libraries... a vision for ukzn libraries*. Retrieved from makerspaces" in academic libraries... a vision for ukzn libraries: <http://libwebteam.blogspot.com/2019/06/makerspaces-in-academic-libraries.html>
- Kurti, R. S., Kurti, D., & Fleming, L. (2014). Practical Implementation of an Educational Makerspace: Part 3 of Making an Educational Makerspace. *Teacher Librarian*, 20-24.
- Ladan, B. F., & Adamu, R. (2023). University Librarians' Opinions on Planning and Developing a Makerspace in their Academic Libraries. *NLA Book of Abstract Final*, 1-12.
- Lathan, J. (2020, July 5). *University of San Diego*. Retrieved from STEAM Education: A 21st Century Approach to Learning: <https://onlinedegrees.sandiego.edu/steam-education-in-schools/>
- Lee, R. J. (2017). Campus-Library Collaboration with Makerspaces. *Public Services Quarterly*, 13(2), 108-116. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/15228959.2017.1303421>
- Okuonghae, O. (2019). Creating Makerspaces in Nigerian Libraries: Issues and Challenges. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 9(2), 49-52. Retrieved from www.trp.org.in
- Osawaru, K. E., Dime, A. I., & Okonjo, E. H. (2020). The Right Time for Makerspaces in Nigerian Academic Libraries: Perceived Benefits and Challenges. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(X), 103-115.
- Pisarski, A. (2014). Finding a Place for the Tween: Makerspaces and Libraries. *Association for Library Services to Children*, 12(3), 14-16. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5860/cal.12n3.13>
- Preddy, L. (2013). *School Library Makerspaces: Grades 6-12*. ABC-CLIO: ABC-CLIO, LLC.
- Radniecki, T., & Klenke, C. (2017). Academic Library Makerspaces: Supporting New Literacies and Skills. *ACRL*, 1-10. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/11213/17717>
- Ratislavová, K., & Ratislav, J. (2014). Asynchronous Email Interview as Qualitative Research Method in the Humanities. *Human Affairs*, 24, 452-460.

Sheridan, k. M., halverson, e. R., litts, b. K., brahms, l., -priebe, l. J., & owens, T. (2014). Learning in the Making: A Comparative Case Study of Three Makerspaces. *Harvard Educational Review*, 84(4), 1-28.

STEAMResources. (2020, July 9). *Resources for Current & Future STEAM Educators*. Retrieved from All Education School.com: <https://www.alleducationschools.com/resources/steam-education/>

Wikipedia. (2020, June 25). *Library Makerspaces*. Retrieved from Library Makerspaces: <http://www.wikipedia.com>

Williams, B. F., & Folkman, M. (2017). Librarians as Makers. *Journal of Library Administration*, 57(1), 17-35. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2016.1215676>